

WORLD CONGRESS
ON OSTEOPOROSIS,
OSTEOARTHRITIS AND
MUSCULOSKELETAL
DISEASES

AbstractBook

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EVENT

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P1434

PREVALENCE OF AND FACTORS ASSOCIATED WITH MRSA AMONG PATIENTS WITH HAND INFECTION TREATED IN A PUBLIC TERTIARY HOSPITAL

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Background: Methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* (MRSA) poses significant challenges in managing hand infections, especially in resource-limited settings like the Philippines. Despite its global prevalence, data on MRSA-specific hand infections in Filipino patients remain scarce. This study aimed to determine the prevalence of MRSA and identify associated factors among patients treated for hand infections at a public tertiary hospital.

Methods: A retrospective, cross-sectional study was conducted at Jose B. Lingad Memorial General Hospital from February 2022 to January 2024. Data from 233 patients treated for hand infections were analyzed. Variables examined included demographics, employment status, infection etiology, comorbidities, traditional medicine use, infection location, and classification. Statistical analyses were performed to identify associations with MRSA.

Results: MRSA prevalence was 30%, with bite wounds and use of traditional medicine showing significant associations ($p = 0.002$). Educational attainment was also linked to MRSA status, with unschooled individuals having a higher prevalence ($p = 0.027$). Other variables, such as age, gender, employment, comorbidities, and infection classification, showed no significant associations.

Conclusion: This study highlights the high prevalence of MRSA in hand infections, with traditional medicine use and bite wounds as key risk factors. The findings underscore the need for targeted educational campaigns, early intervention protocols for bite wounds, and community engagement to address traditional medicine practices. These measures could improve MRSA management and prevention in similar settings.

P1435

THE INFLUENCE OF AGE, GENDER, AND THE UPPER EXTREMITY ANTHROPOMETRY ON THE PALMAR GRIP STRENGTH IN PATIENTS SUFFERING FROM RHEUMATOID ARTHRITIS

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Objective: To examine the influence of age, gender, and upper extremity anthropometry on the palmar grip strength in patients with

rheumatoid arthritis (RA).

Material and methods: This 6-month prospective study included 56 patients of both sexes treated at the Special Hospital for Rheumatic Diseases in Novi Sad, Serbia. All participants signed an informed consent form and completed a sociodemographic questionnaire compiled by the researcher. They also underwent tape measurements (cm) to establish total upper limb length, the length of the upper arm, forearm, and hand, and the wrist and hand circumference for both upper limbs. The palmar grip strength (kg) was evaluated using the Baseline Mechanical Pinch Gauge dynamometer via three measurements separated by 60 s breaks. The relationship between two numerical variables was examined via the non-parametric Spearman correlation coefficient, with $p \leq 0.05$ indicating statistical significance. Statistical processing and analyses were performed using the SPSS ver. 24 statistical package.

Results: All participants (92.9% women, average age 63) were right-handed. No statistically significant correlation between the palmar grip strength in either hand and age was noted ($p > 0.05$). However, male subjects performed statistically significantly ($p = 0.012$) better on the left-hand grip strength test ($Me = 9.17$) compared to females ($Me = 4.75$). Moreover, the right-hand length and the right-hand grip strength were positively correlated ($\rho = 0.290$, $p = 0.030$). The remaining variables, such as upper limb length ($p = 0.137$), upper arm length ($p = 0.433$), forearm length ($p = 0.251$), wrist circumference ($p = 0.263$), and hand circumference ($p = 0.700$), did not show statistically significant correlation with the right-hand palmar grip strength.

Conclusion: Male RA patients, as well as those with a longer right hand, achieved better left-hand palmar grip strength results, which were unaffected by age. In future research, it is necessary to analyze the impact of disease activity and the number of painful and swollen joints of the upper extremities on the palmar grip strength.

P1436

THE INFLUENCE OF BODY HEIGHT AND BODY MASS ON GROSS HAND MUSCLE STRENGTH AND PINCER GRIP IN PATIENTS WITH RHEUMATOID ARTHRITIS

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Objective: To examine the influence of body height and body mass on gross hand muscle strength and pincer grip in patients with rheumatoid arthritis (RA).

Material and methods: The present study, based on a prospective research design, was conducted at the Special Hospital for Rheumatic Diseases in Novi Sad, Serbia, after obtaining approval